

Synthesis and pharmacological evaluation of naproxen and ibuprofen derivatives

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A series of amides of naproxen and ibuprofen were synthesized by condensing different amino acid esters with 2-(6-methoxy-2'-naphthyl) and 2-(4-isobutylphenyl)propionic acids. The synthesized compounds have been evaluated for anti-inflammatory activity and gastrointestinal toxicity which showed good anti-inflammatory activity and considerably reduced G.I. toxicity as compared to the parent drug. The structures of these compounds have been confirmed by physical and spectral analysis.

Non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs (NSAIDs) are used for the treatment of arthritis and all types of pains and trauma. They are contraindicated in gastrointestinal disturbances and their prolonged use leads to gastrointestinal ulceration, bleeding and nephrotoxicity¹, due to the presence of free carboxylic group in the structure. The use of prodrugs to temporarily mask the acidic group of NSAIDs has been postulated as an approach to decrease the gastrointestinal toxicity due to the direct contact effect². Thus in the present study, the carboxylic acid group of naproxen and ibuprofen was temporarily masked by condensing these with amino acids ester. The purpose of using amino acid esters was not only to increase the solubility of resulting amides but also to impart good anti-inflammatory activity³. Amino acids used were glycine, cystine and tryptophan.

Results and discussion

Amides of naproxen and ibuprofen were prepared by condensation of naproxen and ibuprofen acid chloride with various amino acid methyl esters. Propionic acid chlorides were prepared by refluxing the acids with thionyl chloride under anhydrous conditions⁴. Methyl esters of corresponding amino acids were prepared by Ronald's procedure⁵. Finally the amide derivatives were synthesized by modified Scotten-Baumann reaction⁴. The amides exhibited characteristic IR spectral data in agreement with earlier reported data⁴. The ¹H NMR spectra also showed expected signals. The compounds were screened for anti-inflammatory activity and gastrointestinal toxicity. All the compounds were found to possess good activity and were less irritating to the gastric mucosa than the parent drugs.

Anti-inflammatory activity :

The compounds were screened for their anti-inflammatory activity by hind paw method⁶. Carragenin, an irritant was injected subcutaneously into the hind paw of the albino rats at a concentration of 1 mg ml⁻¹ to produce the edema. The standard drug naproxen and ibuprofen (50 mg/kg b. wt) and the test drugs at dose level of 100 mg/kg b. wt were used. The results were quite impressive in naproxen and ibuprofen derivatives in which carboxylic acid group has been replaced by amide analogues showing 72, 64, 54, 64, 54 and 48% inhibition at 100 mg kg⁻¹ oral dose after 3 h (**3a**, **3b**, **3c**, **6a**, **6b** and **6c**) respectively. It was observed that among the active compounds glycine amide of naproxen and ibuprofen (**3a**, **6a**) were most active and activity decreased in cystine derivative (**3b**, **6b**) while tryptophan derivative (**3c** and **6c**) had comparable activity to the standard drugs.

Gastrointestinal toxicity :

The compounds were screened for ulcerogenic activity by reported method⁷. Albino rats were used in all experiments. The compounds were administered orally by gavage in a volume of 10 ml kg⁻¹. Dose equivalent to 40 mg kg⁻¹ of naproxen and ibuprofen and their derivatives were used.

The mean number of ulcer formed in gastric mucosa following oral administration of reference drugs naproxen, ibuprofen and their derivatives (**3a**, **3b**, **3c**, **6a**, **6b**, **6c**) were counted. Drug derivatives showed 2.50, 2.55, 2.70, 3.5 and 3.6 ulcer as compared to 3.90 and 4.60 of naproxen and ibuprofen respectively. It was thus concluded that all the proposed derivatives were significantly less irritating to the gastric mucosa than the parent NSAIDs.

Experimental

M.ps. were recorded in open capillary tubes on electrically heated block and are uncorrected. IR spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Hitachi 270-30 spectrophotometer and ^1H NMR spectra (DMSO- d_6) on a Bruker spectrometer (200 MHz), using TMS as an internal standard.

The acid chloride⁴: To the acid (0.030 mol) in dry chloroform (60 ml) was added thionyl chloride (0.050 mol) and the mixture was refluxed for 4 h. After completion of the reaction the excess of thionyl chloride was distilled off with dry benzene to get the acid chloride.

The methyl ester hydrochloride of amino acids were prepared as reported in literature⁵.

2-[(6-Methoxy-2'-naphthyl)- α -methylacetamido]methylpropionate (3a)⁴: The glycine methyl ester (0.0035 mol) was dissolved in 10% potassium carbonate solution (10 ml) and stirred till it became clear to get alkaline. 2-(6-Methoxy-2'-naphthyl)propionic acid chloride (0.0044 mol) was added to it and stirred for 2 h. The separated solid was washed with 0.5% cold NaOH solution and dried in air. The naproxen glycinamide methyl ester thus prepared was crystallized from chloroform-petroleum ether as white solid (54%), m.p. 87° , ν_{max} 3300 (NH), 3030 (CH ar), 2900 (CH ali), 1635 (CONH), 1735 cm^{-1} (COOCH₃); δ 1.46 (3H, d, J 6 Hz, CH₃CH), 3.52 (1H, q, CH₃CH), 3.65 (3H, s, OCH₃),

3.75 (2H, d, CH₂COOH), 3.85 (3H, s, OCH₃), 7.50–7.56 (6H, m, ArH), 8.25 (1H, br hump, NH).

Bis-[3-thio-(2'-(6-methoxy-2'-naphthyl)- α -methylacetamido]methylpropionate (3b): White solid (71%), m.p. 105° , ν_{max} 3300 (NH), 3030 (CH ar), 2900 (CH ali), 1635 (CONH), 600–700 (CS), 1735 cm^{-1} (COOCH₃); δ 1.46 (6H, d, J 6 Hz, CH₃CH), 2.90 (4H, d, J 1.8 Hz, SCH₂), 3.52 (2H, q, CH₃CH), 3.65 (3H, s, OCH₃), 3.75 (4H, d, CH₂COOH), 3.85 (6H, s, OCH₃), 7.50 (12H, m, ArH), 8.25 (2H, br hump, NH).

2-[(6-Methoxy-2'-naphthyl)-3-indolyl- α -methylacetamido]methylpropionate (3c): White solid (49%), m.p. 93° , ν_{max} 3400 (NH hetro), 3300 (NH), 3030 (CH ar), 2900 (CH ali), 1635 (CONH), 1735 cm^{-1} (COOCH₃); δ 1.46 (3H, d, J 6 Hz, CH₃CH), 2.03 (2H, d, J 5 Hz, CH₂), 3.52 (1H, q, CH₃CH), 3.65 (3H, s, OCH₃), (2H, d, CH₂COOH), 3.85 (3H, s, OCH₃), 7.42 (4H, m, ArH), 7.50 (6H, m, ArH), 8.31 (1H, br hump, NH).

2-[(4-Isobutylphenyl)- α -methylacetamido]methylpropionate (6a): White solid (56%), m.p. 141° , ν_{max} 3300 (NH), 3030 (CH ar), 2900 (CH ali), 1635 (CONH), 1735 cm^{-1} (COOCH₃); δ 0.89 (6H, d, J 6 Hz, (CH₃)₂CH), 1.49 (3H, d, J 8 Hz, CH₃CH), 1.78 (1H, m, (CH₃)₂CH), 2.38 (2H, d, J 6 Hz, CH₂Ar), 3.65 (3H, s, OCH₃), 3.70 (1H, q, CH₃CH), 3.92 (2H, d, J 6 Hz, CH₂COOH), 7.10–7.12 (4H, m, ArH), 8.25 (1H, br hump, NH).

Bis-[3-thio-(2'-(4-isobutylphenyl)- α -methylacetamido]methylpropionate (6b): Low m.p. (61%), ν_{max} 3300 (NH), 3030 (CH ar), 1635 (CONH), 2900 (CH ali), 1635 (CONH), 1735 cm^{-1} (COOCH₃); δ 0.89 (12H, d, J 6 Hz (CH₃)₂CH), 1.49 (6H, d, J 8 Hz, CH₃CH), 1.78 (2H, m, (CH₃)₂CH), 2.90 (4H, s, SCH₂), 2.38 (4H, d, J 6 Hz, CH₂Ar), 3.65 (3H, s, OCH₃), 3.70 (1H, q, CH₃CH), 3.92 (4H, d, J 6 Hz, NHCH₂COOH), 7.10 (8H, m, ArH), 8.30 (1H, br hump, NH).

2-[(4-Isobutyl phenyl)-3-indolyl- α -methylacetamido]methylpropionate (6c): Low m.p. (53%), ν_{max} 3300 (NH), 3030 (CH ar), 2900 (CH ali), 1635 (CONH), 1735 cm^{-1} (COOCH₃); δ 0.89 (6H, d, J 6 Hz, (CH₃)₂CH), 1.49 (3H, d, J 8 Hz, CH₃CH), 1.78 (1H, m, (CH₃)₂CH), 2.03 (2H, d, J 5 Hz, CH₂), 2.38 (2H, d, J 6 Hz, CH₂Ar), 3.65 (3H, s, OCH₃), 3.70 (1H, q, CH₃CH), 3.92 (1H, q, J 6 Hz, CH₂COOH), 7.10 (4H, m, ArH), 7.42 (4H, m, ArH).

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